

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B473
 Date: 01 August 2009
 Take Off: 07:37:57 Z Basel
 Landing: 10:48:25 Z Basel
 Flight Time: 3h 10m 28s

Campaign: CAVIAR
Operating Area: Jungfraujoch

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM	
5	Mission Scientist 1	Stuart Newman	Met Office	
6	AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
8	Core Chem/Nox	Stephane Bauguitte	FAAM	
9	SWS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	
10	ARIES/FWVS	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office	
11	MARSS	James Bowles	Met Office	
12	Mission Scientist 2	Chawn Harlow	Met Office	
13				
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
ViRC chat log	poor comms meant no useful ViRC during CAVIAR
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
CVI	No log as o operator on CAVIAR

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	03 Nov 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_081604_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_091802_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_102114_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_112107_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_081601_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_081804_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_091945_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_102110_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B473
 Date: 1/8/09
 Project:CAVIAR
 Location:Jungfraujoch

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
071507		startup	0.80 kft	186	
072158		tow	0.80 kft	211	
073134		taxy	0.80 kft	335	
073757		T/O	0.77 kft	153	
075425	080324	Run 1	15.0 kft	137	
080123		ovhd jfj	15.0 kft	147	
080325	080802	Profile 1	15.0 - 19.0 kft	147	
080605		Profile 1	18.0 kft	226	interrupt
080659		Profile 1	18.0 kft	313	resume
080802	081836	Run 2	19.0 kft	328	
081847	082354	Profile 2	19.0 - 24.0 kft	323	
082355	083326	Run 3	24.0 kft	143	
082645		Sonde 1	24.0 kft	145	
083155		ovhd jfj	24.0 kft	148	
083520	083949	Profile 3	24.0 - 27.0 kft	126	
083817		Profile 3	27.0 kft	327	interrupt
083846		Sonde 2	27.0 kft	323	
083949	084301	Run 4	27.0 kft	319	
084052		Sonde 3	27.0 kft	319	
084308	084401	Profile 4	27.1 - 28.0 kft	316	
084401	084744	Run 5	28.0 kft	313	
084801	085033	Orbit 1	28.0 - 28.1 kft	332	
085059	085331	Orbit 2	28.1 - 28.0 kft	015	
085351	091436	Profile 5	28.0 - 34.2 kft	033	
090635		ovhd jfj	33.9 kft	148	
091552	092244	Run 6	35.0 - 35.1 kft	359	replaces R6
091602		Sonde 4	35.0 kft	358	
091808		Sonde 5	35.0 kft	316	
092838	093610	Run 7	35.1 - 35.0 kft	150	
093048		Metop	35.0 kft	148	Overpass at 0930
093059		Sonde 6	35.0 kft	148	
093445		Sonde 7	35.0 kft	147	
094225	094519	Run 8	35.1 - 35.0 kft	320	
094520	100638	Profile 6	35.0 - 15.0 kft	322	
095901		Profile 6	21.0 kft	245	interrupt
095933		Profile 6	21.1 kft	285	resume
100704	100841	Orbit 3	15.1 kft	343	
100917	101053	Orbit 4	15.1 kft	034	
101315	101547	Run 9	15.0 kft	162	
101323		ovhd jfj	15.0 kft	163	
101933	103134	Run 10	15.1 - 15.0 kft	317	
102015		ovhd a	15.0 kft	324	
102312		ovhd jfj	15.0 kft	320	
104825		Land	0.82 kft	153	Basel

B473 05:01:45-10:50:19

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

Sortie brief for FAAM

CAVIAR detachment 2009

Flight no:	B473
Proposed date:	Saturday 1 August 2009
Prepared by:	Stuart Newman
Version no.:	1.0, prepared 31 July 2009

Aim:	To sample intensively the water vapour structure of the atmosphere above the Jungfrauoch, and measure the radiative signature of the water vapour continuum. Coincident with an overpass of the European MetOp satellite.
Airfield:	Basel
Flight location:	Swiss Alps in vicinity of Jungfrauoch high altitude research station.
Weather conditions required:	Clear sky (or very nearly clear sky, preferably $\frac{1}{8}$ cloud or less) from surface to space.
Dropsondes:	7 required.

Further sortie details

Coordinates: aim to fly straight and level runs between fixed coordinates

BADEP = 47° 1.6' N, 7° 25.5' E

(Jungfrauoch = 46° 32.9' N, 7° 59.1' E)

A = 46° 22.0' N, 8° 10.0' E

The runs are of approx. 10 mins duration, may be slightly longer at the lowest altitudes.

Orientation: Track approx. 142°T and reciprocal over Jungfrauoch and neighbouring glacier.

Radiometers: ARIES and TAFTS to coordinate their upward and downward views during the straight and level runs. SWS to scan a range of angles except during orbits.

Note that the following flight altitudes are examples only, and in practice these will be chosen by the mission scientist.

Satellite overpass at 0930Z.

Sortie profile

No.	Item	Time	Cumulative time
1	Take off from Basel at 0730Z (0930L)		
2	Transit to arrive at BADEP at FL150	00:15	00:15
3	Perform SLR (BADEP to A) at FL150	00:10	00:25
4	Climbing turn to FL190, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less	00:05	00:30
5	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL190	00:10	00:40
6	Climbing turn to FL240, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less	00:05	00:45
7	Perform SLR (BADEP to A) at FL240, drop one sonde (near BADEP)	00:10	00:55
8	Climbing turn to FL280, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less	00:10	01:05
9	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL280, drop two sondes (near A and JFJ)	00:10	01:15
10	Perform two orbits with angle of bank greater than SZA	00:10	01:25
11	Straight climb (BADEP to A) to FL350, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less	00:20	01:45
12	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL350, drop two sondes (near A and JFJ) - satellite overpass occurs at 0930Z	00:10	01:55
13	Procedural turn for reciprocal run	00:05	02:00
14	Reciprocal SLR (BADEP to A) at FL350, drop two sondes (near BADEP and JFJ)	00:10	02:10
15	Reposition from A to Jungfrauoch, perform short SLR over glacier	00:05	02:15
16	Perform spiral descent from FL350 to FL150 over the Jungfrauoch at 1000 ft/min	00:20	02:35
17	Perform two orbits with angle of bank greater than SZA	00:10	02:45
18	Reposition from Jungfrauoch to A, perform short SLR over glacier	00:05	02:50
19	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL150	00:15	03:05
20	Return to Basel	00:15	03:20

Mission scientist debrief for CAVIAR flight B473 on 1 August 2009

S. M. Newman

Debrief

This flight was planned to investigate the radiative signature of the water vapour continuum, in coordination with solar-tracking FTS measurements performed by NPL at the Jungfraujoch high-altitude observatory. An overpass of the MetOp satellite occurred during the sortie.

Weather conditions were good, with the broken altocumulus seen on take-off from Basel absent from the operating area. A route from the airway point BADEP to the Italian border, intersecting the Jungfraujoch, was flown at various levels to monitor the variation of radiation with changing water vapour amount.

The first run at Flight Level 150 (the minimum permitted) revealed clear sky conditions from surface to space over the plain between BADEP and the Jungfraujoch, with a complete cover of stratocumulus south of the mountains below the observatory altitude of 11,300 ft. PCASP reported significant aerosol on take-off but the air appeared to be very clean in the free troposphere.

Further runs at FL190 and FL240 were carried out in near-perfect clear sky conditions; there appeared to be some structure in the sky near the sun, but this may have been an illusion given the dryness of the air we encountered on the flight. A sonde was dropped at FL240 revealed a dry atmosphere above the shallow boundary layer.

An interrupted profile climb (due to air traffic) necessitated the next run to be started at FL270, with an adjustment to FL280 midway along the run towards BADEP (hence dropsondes were released at FL270). Orbits with angle of bank near the solar zenith angle were performed near BADEP, followed by a long and slow climb to FL350. Two runs at FL350 were timed to coincide with an overpass of the MetOp satellite at 0930 UTC – four dropsondes were released, although unfortunately the nearest sonde to the overpass lost all data below approx. 450 hPa. Extremely low frost points (sub -60°C) were recorded by FWVS, which appeared to be more responsive than the General Eastern hygrometer.

A spiral descent over the Jungfraujoch from FL350 to FL150 was followed by a run at FL150 to finish the science. Clear sky conditions persisted until the end. The light fuel load designed to achieve high-level runs early in the flight meant the total sortie time was 3:10.

Summary

A very good CAVIAR flight given near-perfect clear sky conditions and a good satellite overpass. ARIES data in particular will be valuable.

Instrument issues

No video was recorded during the flight due to operator error. TAFTS did not fly because liquid helium was not available. ARIES worked well despite problems on the previous flight. One dropsonde (at 0931Z) transmitted only a partial upper-level profile. The NPL Jungfraujoch measurements were affected by ice melt from the observatory roof which comprised their data.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

MISSION SCIENTIST: STUART NEWMAN

Flight No **B473**.....

Date **1/8/2009**.....

Page **1** of **2**.....

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
~0737		TAKE-OFF			Some altocumulus over Basel on take-off, looks to be clearing
075422	R1	FL150	138	46°34, 7°30	altocu., altostratus to left, clear to mountains at all levels [BADEP to A]
080010	"	"	145	46°30, 7°54	Coming over JFS, clear view of observatory with variable Sc beyond mountains (8/8 Sc with variable tops)
080324	end R1	FL150 ↑			Clagged in with Sc south of mountains but below our height? Clear above
080630		FL180			RH has dropped to < 70%
080802	R2	FL190	326	46°18, 8°6	A to BADEP, looks clear above
0812		"			PCASP reported sig. almost on take-off but very clear at this level
081300	"	"	317	46°3, 7°48	Towards BADEP looks completely clear above + below
081836	end R2	FL190 ↑		46°0, 7°24	Clear above + below at BADEP
0821	P ↑	FL210			Increase in RH > 80% in relatively shallow layer
082354	R3	FL240	143	47°0, 7°24	T-23.3, Td-37.3°C Some Ci-looking structure towards sun??
082638					Dropsonde #1 v. difficult to say
083326	end R3	FL240		46°18, 8°6	Variable Sc tops near pt. A
083940	R4	FL270			Start of run and dropsonde #2 at FL270 prior to climb
084054		"			Dropsonde #3
084257	P ↑	FL270 ↑ FL280	317	46°42, 7°42	MIDWAY A TO BADEP CLIMB
084401	R5	FL280	314		T-31.8, Td-SI.2 RH ≈ 70% Clear above + below
084745					Orbits at 40° (SZA ≈ 45°)
		~FL300 ↑			Cloud Phys reports twice as much aerosol at this level as at FL280
08 0905	P ↑	FL334		46°36, 7°48	T-44.9, Td-S2.9°C (FWWS Td -55°C)
091530		FL350		46°18, 8°0	T-49.1, Td-S7.5 (but GE struggling)
09155	R6				
091602					Dropsonde #4
091807					Dropsonde #5

Cloud Physics Flight Log B473

Date: 01/08/09	Operator: KFT	DRS Time: 05:16	DAU1 Time: N/A	DAU2 Time: SET	AUX1 Time: SET	AUX2 Time: SET
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DAU2 Disk space? Y

	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		SID2	
Operated?	Y		Y		Y		Y		N	
Pre-flight checks	Ref V:	4.2!	Vref (>7V):	7.4	El#1 V (>1):	2.3	El#1 V (>1):	1.6	Comms?:	
	Data TX?	Y	Sample flow	1.1	El#32 V (>1):	2.9	El#32 V (>1):	1.9		
			Sheath flow	14	El#64 V (>1):	1.6				
			Spectra ok?	Y						

Just after take-off	Are SAMPLE and RECORD buttons on PADS both green?	Y	Are all heaters on? (Check ammeters and CIP dummy box heater switch).	Y
	Are all PADS instruments enabled and updating?	Y		

NOTE that CTRL+T will insert the current time where the cursor is as long as the cursor is a cursor and not a selected box.

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	SID2	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
												CDP CAL PREFLT 40 AND 15MICRON
												2DC CLEANED W IPA
07:39												HEATERS AND LWC ON.
07:42:43	FL060	0		693	0.22	0		0				
07:44:52	FL080	0		133	0.23	0		0				
07:45:54	FL090	0		80	0.2	0		0				
07:46:44	FL100	0		95	0.24	0		0				
07:47:51	FL110	0		70	0.29	0		0				
07:48:39	FL120	0		110	0.34	0		0				
07:49:16	FL130	0		40	0.20	0		0				
07:50:16	FL140	0		30	0.21	0		0				
07:51:03	FL150	0		35	0.23	0		0				END PROFILE. LWC DAT OBS.
07:56:20	FL150	0		33	0.27	0		0				
08:00:27	FL150	0		43	0.89	0		0				
08:03:27	FL150	0		56	0.21	0		0				END RUN1 START PROFILE 1

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	SID2	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
08:04:14	FL160	0		16	0.20	0		0				
08:05:24	FL170	0		30	0.17	0		0				
08:06:06	FL180	0		16	0.23	0		0				
08:08:03	FL190	0		17	0.20	0		0				START RUN2. LWC DAT OBS.
08:13:01	FL190	0		18	0.15	0		0				
08:16:06	FL190	0		26	0.14	0		0				
08:18:38	FL190	0		22	0.22	0		0				END RUN2.
08:20:02	FL200	0		45	0.29	0		0				COINCIDENT RISE IN 03, CO
08:21:11	FL210	0		25	0.20	0		0				
08:23:05	FL230	0		15	0.23	0		0				
08:23:56	FL240	0		10	0.34	0		0				END PROFILE. LWC DAT OBS.
08:28:00	FL240	0		16	0.24	0		0				
08:31:43	FL240	0		15	0.29	0		0				
08:36:25	FL250	0		10	0.29	0		0				
08:37:27	FL260	0		30	0.22	0		0				O3 STRUCTURE.
08:38:20	FL270	0		10	0.19	0		0				LWC DAT OBS.
08:43:02	FL270	0		18	0.27	0		0				START P4.
08:44:05	FL280	0		7	0.13	0		0				START R5.
08:53:54	FL280	0		10	0.13	0		0				START PROFILE 4 .
08:55:04	FL290	0		18	0.19	0		0				
08:56:14	FL300	0		25	0.17	0		0				
08:59:39	FL310	0		45	0.32	0		0				
09:01:54	FL320	0		8	0.13	0		0				
09:04:28	FL330	0		15	0.18	0		0				
09:07:19	FL340	0		18	0.12	0		0				
09:14:30	FL350	0		22	0.13	0		0				END PROFILE 5. START R6. LWC DAT OBS.
09:17:58	FL350	0		23	0.22	0		0				NOISE STARTING TO APPEAR ON PCASP CH1.
09:21:29	FL350											NOISE OCCASIONALLY SPREADS TO PCASP CH2 TOO.
09:51:26	FL300	0		35	0.27	0		0				NOISE MOSTLY CLEARED.
09:53:07	FL280	0		53	0.23	0		0				
09:56:18	FL240	0		50	0.22	0		0				
09:57:19	FL230	0		25	0.21	0		0				
09:59:04	FL210	0		21	0.13	0		0				
10:00:55	FL200	0		20	0.13	0		0				
10:06:40	FL150	0		39	0.17	0		0				
10:13:36	FL150	0		20	0.18	0		0				

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	SID2	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
10:19:45	FL150	0		17	0.23	0		0				START RUN1
10:31:38	FL150	0		46	0.31	0		0				

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics		Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP (old)	Vref:	N/A	
	Flow:		
2DC	EI#1:	1.5	
	EI#32:	1.9	
PCASP SPP-200	Ref V:	7.3	
	Flow:	OK	
CDP	Laser V:	4.1	
FFSSP	Ref V:	N/A	
SID 3	Laser V:	N/A	
Rack Equipment			Please note SEADAS disk space remaining.700MB

Flight:

B473

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B473

Date: 1/8/09

Instruments

1. RFC not operational
- 2.
- 3.

Aircraft

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) $\frac{1}{4}$ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 1/8/09

Flight No: B 473

Pre-Flighter: PHIL ROSENBERG

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☐	Hangar	Collect spanners	Core Chem - 9/16" & 11/16"
Aircraft Cabin: Power-up				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☒	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
5	☒	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
6	☒	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	☒	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
10	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	No REAR FACINGS FORWARD FACINGS + ODD COLOUR
15	☒	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	☒	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	TURNED ON BY OPERATOR
17	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	☒	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	☒	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	☒	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	☒	Satcom C	Checked	
23	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
24	☒	CNC	Butanol filled	NOT FITTED
25	☒	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
26	☒	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	NOT OPERATED
27	☒	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	NOT FITTED
28	☒	3786 CPC	DI Checked / Topped up	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
29	☒	CCN Water	Supply filled / Drain empty	NOT FITTED
30	☒	CCN SS cols A & B	Set to manual A0.2, B0.1	
31	☒	CCN Pressure	Normally set to 650mb	
32	☒	CCN Flow Ratios	A & B = 10 ± 0.3	
33	☒	3786 CPC	Drained	
34	☒	CPC Laptop	AIM Software set up	
External Checks				
35	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd. Photo taken	
36	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
37	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
38	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
39	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
40	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
41	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
42	☒	WAS Bottles	No. fitted and position.	NOT FITTED
43	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
44	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
45	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	NOT REQUIRED
46	☒	All other covers	Removed	
47	☒	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
48	☐	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
49	☐	Tools	Avalon informed	
50	☐			
Avalon Checks				
51	☒	Upper BBRs	Checked & Cleaned	
52	☒	ICEX	applied	
53	☒	Turb Probe - Traps	emptied, detail contents -	a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more

Signed
 a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more

ARIES flight log

Flight: 3473

page 1 of 2

Date: 01/08/09

Operator(s): D. TIDDEMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: CAUIAR BASEL, JUNGFRAU JOCH

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
							CN2
							Cursor Nadir Zenith 30s (CH 30s, N 30s, 2 30s) x 0
							CZP
							Cursor Profile Zen
							(CH 20s, 2 20s) x 0
							N30
							Nadir Long Run 30 sec (CH 30s, N 30s) x 327
075425	FL150	CN2		0	71	31	Start script Run 1
080326	FL150	CN2		0	71	31	Stop
080804	FL190	CN2		0	71	30	Start Run 2
081840	FL190	CN2		0	71	31	Stop
082354	FL240	CN2		0	71	31	Start Run 3
083335	FL240	CN2		0	71	31	Stop
083915	FL270	CN2		0	71	31	Start Run 4
084304	FL270	CN2		0	71	31	Stop
084403	FL280	CN2		0	71	31	Start Run 5
084830	FL280	CN2		0	71	31	Stop
084837	Orbit	CZP		0	71	31	Start orbit FL280 38° orbit
085347	FL280	CZP		0	71	30	Stop
0918450	FL350	CN2		0	70	30	Start (gentle turn at start)
091552	FL350	CN2		0	71	31	Run 6 start
092258	FL350	CN2		0	71	30	Stop
092829	FL350	N30		C	71	30	Start for satellite overpass at 09:30
093641	FL350	N30		C	71	30	Stop
093910	FL350	CZP		0	71	31	Start (turning at point A)
094224	FL350	"		0	71	31	SLR A to JFJ
094517	FL350 Orbit dan	"		0	71	30	Speed profile down
100640	FL150	"		0	71	31	48° orbits FL150
101115	FL150	CZP		0	71	31	Stop

7

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	010809	Flight	B473	log pages
Operator(s)	JB	Campaign	CAVIAR			
Departure	Basel	Arrival	Basel			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on					at time	05:24
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	18°C	Ch	18°C	Ch18	18°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on					at time	05:25
Initial target temperatures	Hot	289	Cold	289		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)					at time	06:08 test
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software					at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	07:10:15		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.61	Cold	297.56	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	37.1	30.6	38.6	42.0	42.1	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again					at time	

B473_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog

```

05:46:00.26 --- - - - -
05:46:00.26 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
05:46:00.26 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
05:46:00.26 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B473
05:46:00.26 --- - - - -
05:46:05.50 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
05:46:08.84 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
05:46:09.40 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
05:46:12.85 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
05:46:18.57 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
05:46:21.57 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
05:46:22.96 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
05:46:23.70 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
05:46:25.15 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
05:46:27.63 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
05:46:29.55 SWS - - 40 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
05:46:29.55 SWS - - - 40 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
05:46:32.29 SWS - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:46:33.95 USH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
05:46:35.23 USH - - - 40 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
05:46:35.23 USH - - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
05:46:37.43 USH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:46:39.56 LSH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
05:46:42.23 LSH - - - 40 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
05:46:42.23 LSH - - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
05:46:46.04 LSH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:47:08.73 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
05:47:13.14 SWS - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
05:47:13.18 LSH - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
05:47:13.20 USH - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
05:47:14.07 SWS - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:47:14.30 LSH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:47:14.43 USH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:47:15.70 SWS - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
05:47:15.73 USH - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
05:47:15.73 LSH - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
05:47:16.54 SWS - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:47:16.78 USH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:47:17.00 LSH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:47:18.26 SWS - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
05:47:18.34 USH - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
05:47:18.36 LSH - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
05:47:19.15 SWS - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:47:19.32 USH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:47:19.54 LSH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:47:21.56 USH - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
05:47:21.58 SWS - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
05:47:21.69 LSH - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
05:47:22.42 USH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:47:22.65 SWS - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:47:22.85 LSH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:47:25.70 SWS - - - - Idling
05:47:25.71 LSH - - - - Idling
05:47:25.77 USH - - - - Idling
06:04:35.13 USH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:04:35.14 SWS - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:04:35.14 LSH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:04:36.09 LSH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:04:36.22 SWS - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:04:38.42 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
06:04:43.45 USH - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:04:43.48 SWS - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:04:43.59 LSH - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:04:44.64 USH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:04:44.79 SWS - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:04:45.08 LSH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.

```

06:04:45.97	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
06:04:45.97	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
06:04:45.99	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
06:04:47.29	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
06:04:47.50	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
06:04:47.76	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
06:04:49.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:04:49.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:04:49.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:00:07.35	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:00:07.36	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:00:07.42	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:00:08.39	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:00:08.42	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:00:08.46	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:00:10.55	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:00:23.90	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:00:23.98	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:00:24.13	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:00:24.47	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:00:25.17	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:00:25.63	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:00:26.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:00:26.96	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:00:27.01	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:00:27.06	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:00:27.64	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:00:28.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:00:28.37	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:00:28.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:00:30.26	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:00:30.27	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:00:30.35	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:00:31.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:00:31.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:00:32.04	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:00:32.94	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:00:32.95	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:00:34.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:00:35.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:00:35.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:00:35.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:04:23.39	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -60.000
07:04:34.38	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 90.000
07:04:35.86	SWS	88.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
07:39:48.48	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
07:39:49.61	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
07:39:54.40	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:39:54.41	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:39:54.41	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:39:57.39	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:40:00.89	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:40:05.66	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:40:05.68	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:40:05.72	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:40:06.56	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:40:06.75	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:40:06.94	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:40:08.00	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:40:08.02	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:40:08.08	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:40:08.93	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:40:09.14	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:40:09.31	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:43:23.53	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:43:28.98	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:43:29.06	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:43:29.07	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:43:29.45	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.

07:43:29.65	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:43:29.82	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:43:30.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:43:30.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:43:31.49	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:43:31.51	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:43:31.61	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:43:32.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:43:32.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:43:32.85	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:43:34.90	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:43:34.92	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:43:34.94	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:43:35.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:43:36.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:43:36.23	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:43:37.05	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:43:37.05	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:07.70	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:45:07.76	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:45:07.76	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:45:08.43	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:45:08.61	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:08.82	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:09.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:45:10.23	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:45:10.32	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:45:10.33	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:45:11.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:45:11.33	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:11.54	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:12.95	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:51:46.97	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:51:46.98	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:51:47.04	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:51:47.83	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:51:48.16	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:51:48.36	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:52:01.18	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:52:01.24	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:52:01.27	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:52:02.10	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:52:02.32	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:52:02.49	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:53:19.65	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:53:19.70	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:53:19.72	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:53:20.12	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:53:20.56	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:53:21.04	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:53:21.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:53:22.19	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:53:22.29	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:53:22.31	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:53:22.86	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:53:23.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:53:23.31	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:53:23.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:53:24.36	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:53:24.37	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:54:25.44	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:54:25.87	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
07:54:29.83	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:54:37.82	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:54:41.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 1 from BADEP to A at FL 150
07:54:45.94	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:54:53.96	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:55:02.05	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:55:10.05	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0

07:55:17.91	SWS	-44.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:55:25.92	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:55:33.97	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:55:41.99	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:55:50.05	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:55:58.17	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:56:06.11	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:56:07.75	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:56:07.79	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:56:07.87	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:56:08.61	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:56:08.83	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:56:09.10	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:56:14.15	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:56:22.17	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:56:30.15	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:56:38.26	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:56:46.26	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:56:54.27	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:57:02.31	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:57:10.40	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:57:18.50	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:57:26.53	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:57:34.60	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:57:42.60	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:57:50.64	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:57:58.71	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:58:06.74	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:58:14.79	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:58:22.89	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:58:30.95	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:58:38.93	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:58:46.99	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:58:55.08	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:58:58.57	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:58:58.63	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:58:58.66	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:58:59.26	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:58:59.54	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:58:59.70	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:59:00.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:59:03.06	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:59:03.12	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:59:03.19	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:59:03.23	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:59:03.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:59:04.16	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:59:04.34	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:59:05.24	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:59:11.24	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:59:19.30	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:59:27.36	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:59:35.49	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:59:43.53	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
07:59:51.45	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
07:59:59.46	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:00:07.54	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:00:15.67	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:00:23.67	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:00:31.77	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:00:39.86	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:00:47.97	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:00:55.98	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:01:04.03	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:01:12.05	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:01:20.03	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:01:28.16	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:01:36.29	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:01:44.41	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0

08:01:52.52	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:02:00.55	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:02:08.71	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:02:16.73	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:02:24.78	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:02:32.93	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:02:40.87	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:02:48.97	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:02:56.96	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:03:05.11	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:03:13.13	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:03:21.16	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:03:24.54	SWS	-8.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:03:32.31	SWS	-8.8	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
08:03:39.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
08:05:13.68	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:05:17.94	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:05:17.96	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:05:17.96	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:05:18.81	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:05:19.09	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:05:19.29	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:05:22.32	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:05:22.36	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:05:22.43	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:05:23.22	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:05:23.44	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:05:23.60	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:08:02.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 2 from A to BADEP at FL 190
08:08:03.40	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
08:08:07.42	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:08:13.94	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:08:15.47	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:08:17.66	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:08:17.69	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:08:17.73	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:08:18.34	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:08:18.55	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:08:18.77	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:08:19.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:08:19.73	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:08:19.75	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:08:19.76	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:08:20.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:08:20.84	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:08:21.09	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:08:22.43	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:08:23.62	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:08:31.71	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:08:39.84	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:08:47.87	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:08:56.00	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:09:04.06	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:09:12.18	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:09:20.28	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:09:28.42	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:09:36.52	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:09:44.21	SWS	-43.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:09:52.33	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:10:00.44	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:10:08.56	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:10:16.76	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:10:24.86	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:10:32.99	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:10:41.09	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:10:49.20	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:10:57.31	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:11:05.43	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:11:13.51	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0

08:11:21.59	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:11:29.65	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:11:37.73	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:11:45.90	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:11:54.01	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:12:02.12	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:12:10.23	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:12:18.30	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:12:26.45	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:12:34.54	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:12:42.65	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:12:50.79	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:12:58.87	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:13:07.06	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:13:15.18	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:13:23.23	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:13:31.33	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:13:39.49	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:13:47.60	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:13:55.69	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:14:03.82	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:14:11.87	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:14:19.97	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:14:28.07	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:14:36.28	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:14:36.37	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:14:36.43	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:14:36.46	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:14:37.27	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:14:37.49	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:14:37.66	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:14:44.53	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:14:52.57	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:15:00.74	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:15:08.77	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:15:16.88	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:15:24.95	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:15:33.19	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:15:41.32	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:15:49.41	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:15:56.49	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:15:56.54	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:15:56.64	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:15:57.39	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:15:57.49	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:15:57.65	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:15:57.81	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:16:01.54	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:16:01.58	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:16:01.61	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:16:02.46	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:16:02.64	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:16:02.89	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:16:05.65	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:16:13.72	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:16:21.86	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:16:30.01	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:16:38.12	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:16:46.19	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:16:54.35	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:17:02.52	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:17:10.76	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:17:18.89	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:17:26.98	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:17:35.08	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:17:43.18	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:17:51.28	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:17:59.45	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:18:07.57	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0

08:18:15.76	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:18:23.98	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:18:32.03	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:18:37.60	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:18:44.80	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
08:19:08.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 2
08:20:30.73	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:20:30.80	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:20:30.84	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:20:31.64	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:20:31.86	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:20:32.12	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:20:32.98	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:20:33.00	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:20:33.01	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:20:33.84	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:20:34.11	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:20:34.31	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:20:35.12	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:20:35.12	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:20:35.19	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:20:35.99	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:20:36.23	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:20:36.45	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:23:56.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 3 at FL 240
08:23:57.00	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:23:57.43	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
08:24:01.48	SWS	39.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:24:02.17	SWS	31.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:24:02.90	SWS	22.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:24:03.61	SWS	14.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:24:04.34	SWS	5.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:24:05.09	SWS	-3.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:24:05.82	SWS	-12.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:24:06.55	SWS	-21.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:24:07.29	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:24:08.03	SWS	-38.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:24:08.77	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:24:10.71	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:24:10.75	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:24:10.77	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:24:11.59	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:24:11.76	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:24:12.02	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:24:13.07	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:24:13.15	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:24:13.19	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:24:13.93	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:24:14.23	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:24:14.44	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:24:16.45	SWS	44.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:24:24.61	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:24:32.78	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:24:40.89	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:24:49.05	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:24:57.10	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:25:05.25	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:25:12.92	SWS	-43.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:25:21.10	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:25:29.21	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:25:37.46	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:25:45.59	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:25:53.79	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:26:01.98	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:26:10.21	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:26:18.33	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:26:26.49	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:26:34.70	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:26:42.76	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0

08:26:50.93	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:26:59.13	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:27:07.24	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:27:15.35	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:27:23.50	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:27:31.67	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:27:39.79	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:27:47.93	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:27:56.08	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:28:04.27	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:28:12.45	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:28:20.69	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:28:28.81	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:28:37.03	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:28:45.26	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:28:53.40	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:29:01.57	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:29:09.70	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:29:17.81	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:29:26.03	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:29:34.21	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:29:42.38	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:29:50.11	SWS	-44.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:29:58.28	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:30:06.49	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:30:14.71	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:30:22.89	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:30:31.09	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:30:39.26	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:30:47.40	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:30:55.61	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:31:03.85	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:31:11.93	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:31:20.09	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:31:28.28	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:31:36.44	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:31:44.61	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:31:52.84	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:32:01.03	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:32:09.26	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:32:17.38	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:32:25.54	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:32:33.67	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:32:41.89	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:32:49.92	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:32:58.05	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:33:06.13	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:33:14.29	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:33:22.52	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:33:29.89	SWS	39.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:33:36.09	SWS	39.1	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
08:33:38.39	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:33:41.64	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:33:44.96	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:33:45.03	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:33:45.06	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:33:45.86	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:33:46.14	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:33:46.37	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:33:47.34	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:33:47.39	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:33:47.41	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:33:48.23	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:33:48.46	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:33:48.73	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:33:49.68	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:33:49.71	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:33:49.73	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:33:50.59	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.

08:33:50.79	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:33:51.01	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:44:03.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 4.2 at FL 280 from A to BADEP
08:44:04.06	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
08:44:08.15	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:44:16.24	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:44:24.40	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:44:32.59	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:44:40.79	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:44:42.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** correction run 5
08:44:48.92	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:44:57.05	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:45:05.13	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:45:13.36	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:45:21.47	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:45:29.64	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:45:37.83	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:45:46.02	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:45:54.20	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:46:02.31	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:46:10.49	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:46:18.66	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:46:26.81	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:46:35.01	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:46:43.26	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:46:48.83	SWS	-17.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:46:55.44	SWS	-17.7	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
08:47:00.31	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
08:47:03.10	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
08:47:05.76	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
08:47:09.75	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:47:09.83	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:47:09.86	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:47:10.62	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:47:10.81	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:47:11.04	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:47:12.42	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:47:12.42	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:47:12.48	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:47:13.10	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:47:13.33	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:47:13.52	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:47:13.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:47:15.23	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:47:15.28	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:47:15.30	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:47:16.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:47:16.33	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:47:16.52	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:47:18.51	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:47:45.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
08:48:01.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit 1 to the right 38 deg
08:50:34.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of orbit 340
08:50:39.52	---	-	-	-	-	***
08:50:39.55	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:50:39.57	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:50:39.62	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:50:40.48	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:50:40.72	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:50:40.88	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:50:41.99	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:50:42.07	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:50:42.12	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:50:42.35	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:50:42.55	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:50:43.43	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:50:43.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:50:43.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:50:45.76	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.

08:50:45.76	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:50:58.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:50:58.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit 2
08:51:25.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** to the right again 37 deg ish
08:53:33.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of orbit
08:53:35.02	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:53:35.05	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:53:35.10	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:53:35.90	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:53:36.14	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:53:36.37	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:53:38.67	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:53:38.72	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:53:38.74	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:53:39.55	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:53:39.72	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:53:39.94	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:53:41.75	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:53:41.79	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:53:41.80	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:53:42.23	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:53:42.63	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:53:43.05	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:53:43.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:53:54.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
08:55:49.86	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:58:32.14	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:58:32.23	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:58:32.24	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:58:33.00	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:58:33.30	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:58:33.51	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:05:18.36	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:05:18.39	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:05:18.46	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:05:19.23	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:05:19.53	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:05:19.75	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:10:49.29	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:10:49.34	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:10:49.35	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:10:49.98	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:10:50.16	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:10:50.41	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:10:50.89	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:10:50.94	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:10:51.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:10:51.13	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:10:51.78	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:10:52.17	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:10:52.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:10:54.25	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:10:54.28	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:10:54.38	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:10:55.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:10:55.39	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:10:55.57	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:10:56.46	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:10:56.51	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:10:56.60	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:10:57.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:10:57.56	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:10:57.78	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:10:58.41	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:14:39.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 6 from A to BADEP at FL 350
09:14:40.10	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
09:14:43.59	SWS	-44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:14:49.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:14:51.29	SWS	44.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0

```

09:14:59.47 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:15:07.17 SWS 43.7 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:15:14.86 SWS -44.2 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:15:23.12 SWS 45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:15:30.81 SWS -43.9 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:15:33.98 --- - - - *** stray reflec and satu between 20 and 40
deg
09:15:39.07 SWS 45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:15:39.15 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
09:15:39.17 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
09:15:39.25 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
09:15:40.04 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
09:15:40.34 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
09:15:40.58 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
09:15:44.65 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
09:15:44.71 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
09:15:44.71 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
09:15:45.55 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
09:15:45.72 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
09:15:45.98 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
09:15:46.77 SWS -43.9 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:15:54.96 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:15:56.15 --- - - - *** start of run
09:16:02.68 SWS -44.2 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:16:10.84 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:16:18.53 SWS -43.9 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:16:26.80 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:16:35.01 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:16:42.72 SWS 44.2 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:16:50.44 SWS -44.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:16:58.66 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:17:06.36 SWS -43.9 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:17:14.59 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:17:22.29 SWS -43.9 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:17:29.98 SWS 43.9 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:17:38.23 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:17:46.46 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:17:54.69 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:18:02.87 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:18:10.54 SWS -43.9 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:18:18.80 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:18:27.02 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:18:35.31 SWS 45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:18:43.53 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:18:49.72 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:18:51.76 SWS 45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:18:52.70 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:18:59.93 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:19:06.16 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:19:08.21 SWS 45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:19:09.10 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:19:15.90 SWS -43.9 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:19:22.17 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:19:24.20 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:19:25.16 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:19:32.43 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:19:38.73 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:19:40.17 SWS 44.3 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:19:41.70 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:19:48.41 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:19:56.60 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:20:04.41 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:20:12.56 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:20:20.24 SWS -43.9 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:20:28.47 SWS 45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:20:36.69 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:20:44.94 SWS 45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:20:53.20 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:20:58.14 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.

```

09:20:58.18	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:20:58.18	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:20:59.03	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:20:59.35	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:20:59.53	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:21:00.44	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:21:00.54	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:21:00.55	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:21:00.94	SWS	44.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:21:01.30	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:21:01.53	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:21:01.77	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:21:09.18	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:21:15.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:21:16.91	SWS	44.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:21:18.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:21:25.12	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:21:31.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:21:32.83	SWS	44.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:21:41.01	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:21:47.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:21:49.25	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:21:50.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:21:57.46	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:22:03.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:22:05.72	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:22:05.99	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:22:06.03	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:22:06.18	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:22:06.94	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:22:07.22	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:22:07.40	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:22:13.40	SWS	-43.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:22:19.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:22:21.59	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:22:22.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:22:29.29	SWS	-43.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:22:35.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:22:36.99	SWS	44.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:22:38.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:22:45.18	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:22:46.21	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:22:51.77	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:23:10.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** run ended befor BADEP due to traffic
09:23:13.29	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:23:13.33	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:23:13.38	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:23:13.97	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:23:14.18	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:23:14.37	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:23:14.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:23:16.29	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:23:16.34	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:23:16.36	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:23:17.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:23:17.41	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:23:17.62	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:23:19.15	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:26:50.46	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:26:50.50	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:26:50.54	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:26:51.18	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:26:51.41	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:26:51.62	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:26:52.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:26:54.77	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:26:54.80	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:26:54.89	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:26:55.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

09:26:55.88	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:26:56.12	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:26:58.34	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:28:31.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at FL 350
09:28:31.40	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:28:31.83	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
09:28:35.34	SWS	-43.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:28:43.08	SWS	44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:28:51.27	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:28:59.45	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:29:07.16	SWS	-43.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:29:15.45	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:29:22.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** stray reflec between -20 and -45 ish from
BADEP to A (Run 7)						
09:29:23.63	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:29:26.35	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:29:26.40	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:29:26.44	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:29:26.84	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:29:27.26	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:29:27.69	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:29:27.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:29:31.36	SWS	44.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:29:33.46	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:29:33.48	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:29:33.59	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:29:34.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:29:34.60	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:29:34.82	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:29:37.03	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:29:39.10	SWS	-43.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:29:47.32	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:29:55.09	SWS	-44.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:30:03.35	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:30:11.57	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:30:19.32	SWS	44.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:30:27.51	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:30:35.22	SWS	44.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:30:42.89	SWS	-43.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:30:51.13	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:30:58.85	SWS	-44.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:31:06.60	SWS	44.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:31:14.85	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:31:23.04	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:31:31.35	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:31:39.58	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:31:47.27	SWS	-43.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:31:55.50	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:32:03.21	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:32:10.94	SWS	44.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:32:19.22	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:32:26.95	SWS	44.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:32:34.68	SWS	-44.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:32:42.89	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:32:50.59	SWS	-43.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:32:58.26	SWS	43.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:33:06.50	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:33:14.22	SWS	44.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:33:22.45	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:33:30.26	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:33:38.48	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:33:46.20	SWS	44.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:33:54.03	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:34:01.72	SWS	43.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:34:09.42	SWS	-44.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:34:17.10	SWS	44.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:34:24.80	SWS	-43.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:34:33.03	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:34:41.26	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0

09:34:49.51	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:34:57.22	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:35:05.44	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:35:13.67	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:35:21.91	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:35:29.59	SWS	-43.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:35:37.82	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:35:46.10	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:35:53.83	SWS	44.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:36:01.53	SWS	-44.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:36:09.75	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:36:11.50	SWS	28.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:36:18.93	SWS	28.3	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.000
09:36:45.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** turning for reciprocal short run
09:37:49.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** patchy cloud below
09:37:56.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** some cirrus above
09:39:57.21	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:39:57.28	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:39:57.29	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:39:58.13	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:39:58.44	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:39:58.62	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:39:59.86	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:39:59.93	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:39:59.93	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:40:00.79	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:40:01.00	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:40:01.26	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:40:02.80	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:40:02.85	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:40:02.88	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:40:03.28	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:40:03.69	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:40:04.13	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:40:04.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:40:06.64	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:42:25.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
09:43:25.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 8
09:45:17.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** spiral profile descent to the right
09:49:37.48	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:49:37.54	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:49:37.56	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:49:38.36	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:49:38.64	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:49:38.81	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:50:14.36	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:50:14.38	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:50:14.44	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:50:15.04	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:50:15.31	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:50:15.55	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:50:15.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:50:18.69	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:50:49.53	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.000
09:50:57.30	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:50:57.35	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:50:57.39	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:50:57.78	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:50:58.23	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:50:58.62	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:50:58.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:51:06.68	SWS	3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
09:51:32.55	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:51:32.66	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:51:32.67	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:51:33.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:51:33.64	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:51:33.82	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:51:36.07	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.

```

09:55:24.60 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
09:55:24.64 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
09:55:24.71 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
09:55:25.50 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
09:55:25.78 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
09:55:25.97 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
09:55:28.32 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
09:55:28.34 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
09:55:28.38 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
09:55:29.23 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
09:55:29.42 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
09:55:29.66 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
09:55:30.63 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
09:55:30.71 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
09:55:30.73 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
09:55:31.53 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
09:55:31.78 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
09:55:32.03 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
09:56:28.35 --- - - - - *** for reposition between JFJ and A using
nadir view to look at glacier
09:58:36.45 --- - - - - *** interupt descent at 210
09:58:39.69 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
09:58:39.78 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
09:58:39.80 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
09:58:40.73 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
09:58:40.90 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
09:58:41.15 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
09:59:04.48 --- - - - - *** at 210 now
09:59:42.10 --- - - - - *** resumeing p descent
10:05:47.79 --- - - - -
10:05:47.79 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
10:05:47.79 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
10:05:47.79 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B473
10:05:47.79 --- - - - -
10:05:49.06 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:05:52.25 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:05:55.12 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:05:58.62 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:05:58.71 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:05:58.89 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:06:02.29 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:06:03.91 SWS - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
10:06:03.92 SWS - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
10:06:05.84 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
10:06:08.55 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:06:10.71 USH - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
10:06:10.72 USH - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
10:06:11.60 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
10:06:13.94 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:06:15.17 LSH - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
10:06:15.17 LSH - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
10:06:15.94 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
10:06:20.74 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
10:07:03.62 --- - - - - *** orbit 3 now
10:08:42.94 --- - - - - *** end of orbit 3
10:08:45.98 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
10:08:46.00 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
10:08:46.02 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
10:08:46.25 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:08:46.45 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:08:46.65 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:08:46.87 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
10:08:47.09 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
10:08:47.32 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
10:08:48.46 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:08:52.16 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
10:08:52.18 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
10:08:52.26 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.

```

10:08:53.01	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:08:53.23	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:08:53.45	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:08:54.43	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:08:54.44	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:08:54.50	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:08:55.31	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:08:55.50	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:08:55.73	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:09:13.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:09:18.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit 4 45 deg to right again
10:10:51.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:10:52.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of orbit
10:10:55.62	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:10:55.67	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:10:55.68	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:10:56.09	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:10:56.33	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:10:56.53	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:10:57.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:10:57.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:10:58.40	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:10:58.40	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:10:58.51	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:10:59.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:10:59.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:10:59.75	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:00.57	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:00.57	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:07.00	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:07.85	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:09.72	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:11:11.38	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:11:16.17	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:16.20	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:16.26	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:17.03	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:17.26	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:17.54	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:18.56	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:18.58	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:18.63	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:19.46	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:19.68	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:19.84	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:07.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** run from JFJ to A
10:12:16.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** over land currently
10:13:06.30	---	-	-	-	-	***
10:13:18.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** over JFH
10:13:21.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** JFJ
10:13:27.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** over glaciars
10:14:12.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** over mountains (rock and snow)
10:14:26.75	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:14:26.78	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:14:26.81	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:14:27.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:14:27.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:14:27.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:14:27.70	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:14:27.92	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:14:28.07	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:14:34.64	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:14:39.11	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:14:39.20	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:14:39.21	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:14:40.02	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:14:40.34	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:14:40.48	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:14:42.71	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.

10:14:42.75	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:14:42.76	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:14:43.61	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:14:43.82	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:14:44.03	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:00.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud below
10:15:14.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** over land again
10:15:22.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud
10:15:47.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** now patchy cloud over land
10:15:49.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
10:15:55.90	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:15:59.63	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:15:59.65	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:15:59.71	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:16:00.50	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:16:00.79	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:16:01.00	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:16:02.04	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:16:02.04	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:16:02.10	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:16:02.93	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:16:03.10	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:16:03.36	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:11.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:18:43.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:18:50.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:19:30.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** run from A to BADEP at FL 150
10:19:31.82	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:19:35.99	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:19:36.00	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:19:36.02	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:19:36.65	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:19:36.88	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:37.04	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:37.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:19:38.35	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:19:38.41	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:19:38.47	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:19:39.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:19:39.47	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:39.62	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:40.37	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:43.73	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:19:44.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:19:45.42	SWS	-3.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:19:48.27	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:19:48.32	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:19:48.33	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:19:49.12	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:49.35	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:49.56	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:20:50.15	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:20:50.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:20:51.82	SWS	170.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:20:55.34	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:20:55.35	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:20:55.37	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:20:56.26	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:20:56.43	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:20:56.65	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:09.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** nadir for glaciator again
10:21:44.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** over patchy cloud, and snow covered mountain
10:22:24.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** over glaciator now
10:22:54.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** (edge of) properly over glaciator now
10:23:13.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** JFJ
10:23:24.93	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:23:28.78	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:23:28.80	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.

10:23:28.82	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:23:29.69	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:29.91	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:30.07	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:31.22	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:23:31.24	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:23:31.35	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:23:32.13	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:32.36	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:32.56	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:36.19	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:23:37.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:23:37.87	SWS	-3.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:23:39.43	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:23:39.44	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:23:39.49	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:23:40.34	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:40.56	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:40.77	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:42.05	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:23:42.15	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:23:42.15	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:23:42.94	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:43.10	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:43.34	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:52.19	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
10:25:32.41	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:25:32.82	SWS	-3.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
10:25:34.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:25:37.28	SWS	40.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:25:37.94	SWS	32.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:25:37.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:25:38.66	SWS	23.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:25:39.35	SWS	15.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:25:40.06	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:25:40.78	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:25:41.49	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:25:42.20	SWS	-18.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:25:42.89	SWS	-26.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:25:43.60	SWS	-35.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:25:44.32	SWS	-43.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:25:49.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:25:52.25	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:25:53.26	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:25:53.27	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:25:53.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:25:53.45	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:25:54.15	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:25:54.42	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:25:54.59	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:00.20	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 25.0
10:26:05.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:26:06.43	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:26:12.64	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 25.0
10:26:18.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:26:18.87	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:26:25.09	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:26:30.75	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:26:36.44	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:26:42.08	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:26:47.78	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:26:53.43	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:26:59.12	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:27:04.77	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:27:10.46	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:27:16.19	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:27:21.86	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:27:27.55	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:27:33.22	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0

10:27:38.90	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:27:44.53	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:27:50.23	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:27:55.90	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:28:01.57	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:28:07.21	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:28:12.89	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:28:18.52	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:28:24.21	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:28:29.44	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:28:35.11	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:28:40.78	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:28:46.43	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:28:52.12	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:28:57.75	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:29:03.47	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:29:09.13	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:29:14.74	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:29:20.44	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:29:26.11	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:29:31.79	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:29:37.42	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:29:43.12	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:29:48.78	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:29:53.30	SWS	4.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:29:56.44	SWS	4.9	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
10:29:58.83	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:29:58.84	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:29:58.86	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:29:59.69	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:59.92	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:00.09	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:03.33	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:30:03.41	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:30:03.43	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:30:04.18	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:04.41	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:04.61	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:33:19.59	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:33:19.62	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:33:19.67	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:33:20.50	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:33:20.73	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:33:20.94	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:33:22.18	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:33:22.20	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:33:22.23	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:33:22.66	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:33:23.06	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:33:23.62	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:33:23.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:27.42	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:43:06.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.